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Molecular and Genotoxicity Effect of Certain aqueous Plant Extracts in *elminthosporium Rostratum* as a Phytopathogenic Fungi

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Abstract

The development of natural antifungal treatments by plant extracts is of great importance because of their safe effects on both the human and animal health, besides their antifungal effects against different Phytopathogenic Fungi. The current study aimed to explore the molecular and genotoxicity effect of two aqueous extracts from wild plants *Rumex vesicarius* L. and *Ziziphus spina-christi* aqueous extracts on the leaf spots fungi, *Helminthosporium rostratum*. The fungal strain was treated with 25 mg/ml of each extract then the alteration in both of the amino acids and DNA of the fungus was assessed by different experiments including, Proteomic analysis by SDS-Page, the total amino acids analysis by the high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), DNA profiles analysis by Restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP), Random Amplified Polymorphic DNA (RAPD), and COMET assay. The results showed that 25 unique bands were produced by the plant's extracts, despite, *Ziziphus* extract have more effective than *Rumex*. Besides, the treatments decreased the total amino acid contents dried biomass of *H. rostratum*. Plant Extracts affects the DNA composition wherein RFLP, *Cla* I restriction enzyme could produce 100% polymorphic bands post-treatment, in RAPD, seven polymorphic unique bands were obtained with P-12 primer, and finally, COMET assay showed an observed tailed DNA in the treated fungal nuclei. We concluded that both of the two plants aqueous extracts could induce successful changes in the amino acid composition besides a remarkable genotoxic effect on *H. Rostratum* which highlights their antifungal effect

Key words: *Rumex vesicarius* L; *Ziziphus spina-christi*; *Helminthosporium Rostratum*, Essential and non-essential amino acids; RFLP; RAPD; COMET assay.

INTRODUCTION

Exserohilum rostratum, *Setosphaeria rostrata* or *Helminthosporium rostratum* is a common plant pathogen that causes leaf spots and blights in many cereal crops. This fungus is characterized by the presence of melanin which is thought to be the main reason for its virulence (Kusai et al., 2016). *Helminthosporium*, is also known as *graminicolous* species which are pathogenic to *Oryzoideae*, *Arundinoideae*, *Festucoideae*, *Eragrostoideae*, and *Panicoideae* in the family of *Gramineae* which causes severe economic losses to many types of crops (Saarela et al., 2018). The basic morphology of this fungus consists of solitary, cylindrical,

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unbranched, brown conidiophores that are responsible for the production of pseudo septate conidia and terminal conidia through the conidiophores (Voglmayr and Jaklitsch, 2017).

Natural products derived from higher plants have contributed to pest control in their own right either as crude extracts or in purified form and as starting materials for semi-synthetic derivatives (Stevenson et al., 2017). Many universal regulatory policies had encouraged the development of new natural pesticides and fungicides because of their higher safety levels for human and animal health (Tembo et al., 2018). In Saudi Arabia, the phytochemical screening of the two wild plants *Rumex vesicarius L.* and *Ziziphus spina-christi* extracts showed enrichment with flavonoid compounds such as *rutin*, *quercetin*, *myricetin*, *apigenin*, *quercetin-3-O-enrichment with -galactoside*, *luteolin*, *kaempferol* and *kaempferol-3-O-robinoside* (Abu-Taleb et al., 2011). The flavonoids had many physiological functions including their protective activity against variable microbes, antioxidants, and considered an important developmental regulator through the auxin transport and catabolism (Mouradov and Spangenberg, 2014).

Measurement of DNA damage in nuclei of fungal cells in addition to the alteration of the amino acids is a new area of study to investigate the efficacy of natural or chemical fungicides against specific plant pathogens (Ezeonu et al., 2018). Different techniques such as the Random Amplified Polymorphic DNA (RAPD) (Irfan et al., 2017), Restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) (Guan et al., 2018), and the alkaline single cell gel electrophoresis (comet assay) (Langie et al., 2015) are very sensitive, rapid, easy to handle, noninvasive, visual and inexpensive techniques in the detection of DNA damage. DNA damage might be indicated by the appearance or disappearance of amplification products, point mutations and/or complex chromosomal rearrangements induced by genotoxic chemicals or phytochemicals (Mahboob et al., 2019). In the COMET assay, the length of the comet tail and the head is a reflection of the extent of DNA damage due to the interactions between the pathogenic fungi and fungicide which reflects their efficacy, as well (Langie et al., 2015).

So, in the present study we tried to light focus on the antifungal effect of the aqueous extracts of *Rumex vesicarius L.* and *Ziziphus spina-christi* on the *H. rostratum* fungus. We tested the effect on selected amino acids besides the genetic alterations and DNA damage to study the biochemical response of the fungal cell to aqueous plant extracts.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

1. Chemicals and reagents:

All of the chemical reagents were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Sigma-Aldrich, Saint Louis, Mo, USA).

2. Plants collection and preparation of extracts:

In the current study, two wild plants *Rumex vesicarius L.* and *Ziziphus spina-christi* were collected from the Riyadh area in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The aqueous extracts were prepared as previously described (Abu-Taleb et al., 2011; Ezeonu et al., 2018). In short, the leaves from *Ziziphus sp.* and the aerial shoots from *Rumex sp.* were collected, cleaned, and dried. These dried parts were soaked in an airtight container of distilled water, at the concentration of 9% wt/vol, for 24 hours at room temperature. Later, the containers were agitated for another 24 hours, filtered and the supernatants were re-dried again. The whole solid materials were collected and stored at 4°C, till use. Before use, the powder was re-diluted in distilled water, filtered and sterilized by bacteriological sterile Sartolab® RF Vacuum Filtration Units 180C8 (Sartorius Corporate Administration GmbH, Goettingen, Germany).

3. Fungus and cultures preparation:

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The *H. rostratum* fungus was identified and provided by the Department of Plant Protection, College of Food and Agricultural Sciences, King Saud University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. The fungal cultures were grown regularly in the *Czapak Dox* agar medium and maintained on PDA (Potato Dextrose Agar) slants. The plates were incubated at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ for further experiments (Swapna and Lalchand, 2016).

4. Total phyto-proteins determination:

The total protein estimation was performed by the method of Daughaday and colleagues, 1952 (Daughaday et al., 1952). Briefly, the amount of 0.5g of the fresh plant tissue was hydrolyzed in a saline solution of NaCl, centrifuged, and the supernatant was collected to give the protein fractions. About 100 μl of the protein extract was mixed with a working solution of alkaline copper reagent (4.5 ml of 20% Fehling Solution B prepared in 0.1N NaOH plus 0.5 ml of 0.1% of $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$). The mixture was incubated at room temperature (RT) for 15 min, then mixed with 0.5 ml of the diluted Folin reagent and re-incubated for 30 min RT. The colorimetric estimation of the protein content took place at 750 nm by a common spectrophotometer.

5. Protein extraction and precipitation:

The strain of *H. rostratum* was grown as mentioned above. The sterilized aqueous plant extracts were, separately, added to each plate at a certain dose (25 mg/ml) and incubated at 28°C in a shaking incubator for seven days. One plate was kept untreated to act as a positive control. The fungal biomass, in all plates, were collected, filtered, and dried by cold lyophilization. The lyophilized products were used in further experiments.

6. Proteomic analysis by SDS-Page:

The total protein content in the treated plates were estimated by SDS-PAGE which is slightly modified from Laemmli, 1970 and Sahu and colleagues, 2017 (Laemmli, 1970; Sahu et al., 2017). Briefly, the previously prepared lyophilized products were mixed with the appropriate amount of the 1.5X SDS-PAGE loading buffer, containing leupeptin, pepstatin, and PMSF, in addition to about 300-400 μl of glass beads and incubated on ice. The mixture was vortexed in cold setting and then centrifuged at the maximum speed, where the supernatants were collected. The supernatant was denatured at $95-100^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 min, then 20-30 $\mu\text{l}/\text{lane}$ was loaded into 7% SDS-poly acrylamide gel in the protein electrophoresis apparatus. Proteins were analyzed by the vertical slab SDS-PAGE gel at 130 v for 60 min. The gel was further stained with Coomassie brilliant blue G-250 for 60 min and visualized by the Bio-Rad gel documentation system, Gel Doc 2000 (BIO RAD, Hercules, CA, USA). The band intensity was quantitatively measured by the BIO-RAD Video densitometer (BIO RAD, Hercules, CA, USA). The experiment was performed in triplicates.

7. Amino acid analysis by the high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC):

The HPLC Pico-Tag method was used to estimate the amino acid composition of the fungal samples, as previously described (Cohen et al., 1989; Parasad, 2017). In short, the cold-dried fungal mass, previously prepared, was mixed with 10% (w/v) of HCl and shaken, frequently, for 30 min RT. Further, the extract was cooled, diluted in water, and filtered. The supernatant was mixed with a sodium acetate buffer solution and diastase solution then dried at 45°C to 50°C for 3 hours. The product was remixed with 10% (w/v) HCl and anhydrous sodium sulfate and re-dissolved by heating at 50°C to 55°C . Later, the mixture was washed by 1 ml of isobutene was added, vortexed and centrifuged at 12,000 rpm and repeated triple. The amino acids were analyzed by precolumn derivatization with FMOC-Cl₄ (FLUKA, AG, Switzerland) followed by gradient elution reversed-phase HPLC. For HPLC analysis, the purified mixture in addition to the standard amino acid solutions was derivatized, separated and analyzed by a stainless-steel Pico-Tag amino acid column (Varian Associates Inc., USA) with Spectra-Physics P2000 variable wavelength detector (at 254 nm) (Waters Associates Inc., USA) and Spectra-Physics Data System software, according to the manufacturer instructions.

8. DNA profiles analysis by Restriction fragment length polymorphism (RFLP) analysis:

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The fungal DNA was extracted from the frozen-dried fungus mass, as described before (Lehmann et al., 1992; Aamir et al., 2015). The RFLP analysis was performed as described before (Guan et al., 2018). Briefly, the fungal DNA extract was stabilized and precipitated by Ethanol for 3 hours at -20°C. The precipitate was pelleted and dried briefly under vacuum then re-suspended in DNase-free water, quantified and separated on 0.8% agarose gel electrophoresis for quality and yield assessments. The pure DNA extract was digested by FastDigest® Restriction Enzymes, *Afa I*, *AsiA I*, *Bbu I*, *BshT I* and *Cla I* (ThermoFischer Scientific, USA), according to manufacturer instructions. The digested products were separated on polyacrylamide gels and further stained with Ethidium bromide. The gels were fixed gradually, in 25% ethanol for 30 min then in silver-impregnated for another 30 min. Gels were washed incubated in dark in the developing solution for 10 min then the stop and preserving solution was, frequently, added. Gels were visualized by the Photo Print imaging system (Vilber Lourmat, France) and the bands intensity was detected by Bio-One D++ software (Vilber Lourmat, France). The sizes of DNA fragments were calculated and compared to a molecular DNA marker.

9. Fungal DNA analysis by the Random Amplified Polymorphic DNA (RAPD) PCR:

The extracted Fungal DNA was amplified by RAPD technique as described before (Reinoso and Bettera, 2016). The PCR reaction took place by the Taq DNA polymerase from FastMix/Frenche™ PCR (i-StarTaq) (iNtRON Biotechnology inc., South Korea) and random RAPD Primers (Carl Roth GmbH + Co. KG - Karlsruhe, Germany) as shown in **Table 4**. The PCR conditions were as follows; Initial denaturation at 94°C for 4 min, 39 cycles of 45 s at 94°C, 45 s at 35°C, and 1 min 30 s at 72°C, then the final extension at 72°C for 5 min using the MyCycler™ Thermal Cycler System (BIO RAD, Hercules, CA, USA). The PCR products were separated and analyzed on 2% agarose gel electrophoresis. The binary data generated here were used to estimate levels of polymorphism by dividing the polymorphic bands by the total number of scored bands. The experiments were repeated triple.

10. COMET ASSAY (SCGE) method:

The DNA damage was detected by the COMET assay as had been described elsewhere with minor modifications (Olive and Banáth, 2006; Kawaguchi et al., 2010; Langie et al., 2015) Briefly, The dried fungal mass was suspended in S-buffer (1M Sorbitol, 25 mM NaH₂PO₄, pH 6.5) and then mixed with 0.7% agarose containing Zymolyase. The mixtures were spread as microgels on sterile microscopic slides. The microgels were incubated at 4°C for 5 min. and at 37°C for 10 min., respectively (to form the fungal spheroplasts). Later, the slides were submerged in a lysis solution (1M NaCl, 50 mM EDTA, 30 mM NaOH, 0.1% N -lauroyl Sarcosine; pH 10) for 1 hour at 4°C, washed with a denaturing solution (30 mM NaOH, 10 mM EDTA; pH 12.6), and subsequently subjected to electrophoresis (0.45 V/cm) in the same denaturing solution for 15 minutes. Gels were visualized by an epifluorescence microscope where the extent of DNA damage was assessed quantitatively by Komet software Version 3.1. (Kinetic Imaging, Liverpool, UK). The percentage of tail DNA (TD %) and tail moments TM (fraction of migrated DNA multiplied by some measure of tail length) expressed the total DNA damage.

11. Statistical Analysis:

The statistical analysis was performed by STATISTIX software. Both *one-way ANOVA* and *Duncan* tests were used to calculate the significance levels of the interpreted data. The *P values* were considered significant at *P*<0.05.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Plant Extracts induced a Biochemical Alterations in *H. Rostratum*:

The changes in the cellular proteins might be a reflection of any other alteration or damage induced to DNA (Salem, 2016). These changes might be contributed to the changes induced in the phenotypic structure of an

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organism, the malfunction of the structural and enzymatic components of the cells, and the developing of several pathogens (Krisiko and Radman, 2019). In other words, any changes in the proteomic systems might be the mirror image of the genetic variations.

In the current study, both of the two aqueous extracts exhibited a distinctive, quantitative, and qualitative alterations in electrophoretic banding pattern of total proteins yielded from treated fungal mycelium compared to untreated control. Protein alterations based on changes in bands molecular weights (MWs), bands intensities, fractionation of some bands, the appearance of new bands (unique bands) and disappearance of other bands (polymorphic bands) as shown in **Table 1** and **Figure 1**. The SDS-PAGE analysis revealed 42 total polypeptides bands with different (MWs) ranged from 26 to 246.06 KDa and a total polymorphism of 96.69%. The results showed 25 new bands (75.76%) that were considered unique while another seven bands (21.2%) were considered polymorphic and one single band (3.03%) was considered monomorphic at 79.63 KDa. In the setting of *Ziziphus* aqueous extract treatment, a total of 16 peptides was detected from which eight new unique peptides were shown at the sizes of 162.80, 143.88, 124.23, 104.28, 99.11, 61.07, 59, and 26 KDa. In the case of *Rumex* aqueous extract treatment, the proteins were separated into 15 peptides, from which 9 bands were unique with the sizes of 236.48, 193.89, 155.22, 145.51, 123.53, 115.44, 104.87, 97.47, and 61.37 KDa. Moreover, the results of protein profiles showed that both plant extracts suppressed the expression of certain proteins (216.69, 124.94, 95.36, 74.58, 56.1 KDa) as compared to the control treatment. Most of the polymorphic peptides (~72%, 5 bands) were shown in the results of *Rumex* and *Ziziphus* extracts while two peptides at 151.57 and 114.79 KDa were specific to control and *Ziziphus*. The results indicated that plant extracts treatments cause alterations in the relative mobility of bands, intensities, expression of new protein and suppression of some proteins. Moreover, the obtained result revealed that *Ziziphus* extract have more effective than *Rumex* extract on gene expression of the fungus.

The reduction of some protein's expression occurred following the treatment with the tested plant extracts, indicated a strong modification in overall cell energy metabolism and protein synthesis. These alterations are based on variations in molecular weights and intensities of polypeptides bands as well as gain or loss of protein bands that led to high levels of protein polymorphism. The resulting unique bands or even the disappearance of some others might be due to either the expression of new mutations at the regulatory system of unexpected genes which induce different translations of the mRNA and consequently, different amino acids sequence and different proteins formed or disappeared. Furthermore, the changes in band intensity could be interpreted based on gene duplication or point mutation, as well, because it might lead to more or less expression of specific proteins. In the same trend, a recent study showed that the Hydroalcoholic Extract of *Platonia insignis* leaves could cause a DNA alteration of different *Candida* species that causes the release of different pro-apoptotic factors due to the rupture of the mitochondrial membrane (da Silva et al., 2020). Another study showed that the ethanolic extract of *Ziziphus* could induce significant growth inhibition of *Candida albicans*, *Candida tropicalis*, *Cryptococcus neoformans*, and *Microsporium canis* which might be due to the genetic alteration (Al-Ali and Al-Judaibi, 2019). Another study showed that the butanol extract of the *Sapindus saponaria* fruits could induce changes in protein abundance of *C. albicans* (Fiorini, 2016). More studies have shown similar effects (Abd-Elaah and Ahmed, 2005; Abd-Elaah et al., 2006; Coumans et al., 2011).

2. Plant Extracts changed the amino acids profile of *H. Rostratum*:

Amino acids are divided into two categories; Essential amino acids (EAAs) which are usually synthesized by plants and non-essential amino acids (NEAAs) which synthesized by all organisms (Kumar et al., 2017). The acquisition of amino acids by fungal pathogens interferes with several sensory and uptake systems which suggest the usage of these amino acids as a targeting factor that may trigger the fungal hyphal morphogenesis, capsule formation, and melanization (Garbe and Vylkova, 2019).

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In the current study, a remarkable quantitative variation of the EAAs, NEAAs and total amino acid composition of *H. rostratum* had been reported, Table 2. HPLC analysis of *H. rostratum* revealed the presence of 17 amino acids, from which nine (52.6%) EAAs (*Arginine, Histidine, leucine, Isoleucine, lysine, Methionine, Phenylalanine, Threonine, and valine*) and eight (44.4%) NEAAs (*Alanine, Asparagine, Aspartic acid, Cysteine, Glutamic acid, Glutamine, Proline, and Tyrosine*) had been detected. Their amount in each aqueous plant extracts treatments were varied from each other compared with control (untreated). These variations may reflect plant extract stress on treated fungal growth. Arginine was recorded as the most represented EAA by 7.321 $\mu\text{mol}/100\text{mg}$ of the dry biomass compared to Glutamic acid by 4.029 $\mu\text{mol}/100\text{mg}$ as NEAA.

Both of the two plants extract induced a remarkable alteration in the amino acid level. The total amino acids contents decreased from 25.651 $\mu\text{mol}/100\text{mg}$ in the untreated control to 21.445 $\mu\text{mol}/100\text{mg}$ and 21.692 $\mu\text{mol}/100\text{mg}$ of dried biomass of *H. rostratum* treated with *Rumex* and *Ziziphus*, respectively. In the reading of EAAs, it was noticed that treatments by both extracts induced a slight reduction in the amino acid levels except for Methionine and Phenylalanine that showed a slight increase. Similarly, for NEAAs all the levels decreased after treatments except for Glutamine and Proline. On the other hand, it was noticed that the treatment with *Rumex* showed more reduction in the EAA levels, by 9.759 $\mu\text{mol}/100\text{mg}$ compared to 11.386 $\mu\text{mol}/100\text{mg}$ of the control, while *Ziziphus* induced more effects on the NEAA's by 10.861 $\mu\text{mol}/100\text{mg}$ compared to 14.265 $\mu\text{mol}/100\text{mg}$ of the untreated biomass. The deep analysis revealed that the most affected EAAs were isoleucine and leucine by a reduction of 47.6% and 27.4%, respectively after *Rumex* treatments and a reduction of 33.8% and 45%, respectively after *Ziziphus* treatments. In the case of NEAAs, *Cysteine* and *Alanine* were the most amino acids affected by *Rumex* treatment with 37.6% and 28.8% decline, respectively, while *Glutamic acid* and *Asparagine* amino acids were the most affected by *Ziziphus* treatment with 45.4% and 36.8% decline, respectively. The results showed an increase in the *Proline* content by 25% and 28% after the treatment of *Rumex* and *Ziziphus*, respectively. The different composition of *Rumex* and *Ziziphus* extracts may explain the variable effect on the content of the amino acid and further the effect on the structural and enzymatic components of membranes and organelles of *H. rostratum*.

Production of Reactive Oxygen Species (ROS) by the degenerative oxidation of proteins and amino acids caused because of the alteration of sulfhydryl group in cysteine, methionine, and tryptophan (Sharma and Graham, 2010) or the reduction of carbonyl or carboxyl groups such as in Arginine, Histidine, Lysine, Threonine and Tryptophan, which may reduce their production causing their malfunction (Davies, 2016). In a similar interpretation, a previous study showed that leaf extract of *Bucida buceras* has a strong antioxidant effect against the *Penicillium expansum*, *Penicillium janthinellum*, *Trichoderma harzianum* and *Fusarium oxysporum* (Mahlo et al., 2016). A recent study showed the strong in vitro antioxidant activity of the methanolic, ethanolic and aqueous extracts of the leaves of extracts of *Ziziphus spins-christi* as indicated by Folin-Ciocalteu procedure because of its phenolic content (Khaleel et al., 2016). Another study showed the two new fungicides *diniconazole* and *tebuconazole* had a strong antioxidant effect on *Alternaria alternata*, *Fusarium graminearum* and *Pyrenophora tritici-repentis* species (Shomeet et al., 2018). One other study showed that the phenolic composition of the *Myrcia splendens* leaves, which is similar to *Ziziphus* and *Rumex* composition, induced an evaluated the antifungal and antioxidant potential against *Alternaria alternata* (Pontes et al., 2019).

3. Plant Extracts affects the DNA composition of H. Rostratum:

RFLP analysis of generated DNA fragments enables botanists to study the structural changes in the whole genomic DNA, and consequently, the variation in gene expression induced by different pathogens or treatments which can distinguish between different species and genotypes (Nybom et al., 2014). The genomic DNA of *H. rostratum*, was digested with five restriction enzymes (*Afa I, AsiA I, Bbu I, BshT I and Cla I*), to be used in the RFLP analysis as shown in **Table 3** and **Figure 3**. The five restriction enzymes had generated 42 different fragments of DNA. It was noticed that all enzymes, except *Cla I*, had a monomorphic band while only

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Bbu I and *BshT I* had a polymorphic band with 50% total polymorphism. *Cla I* could produce 100% polymorphic bands, total 9 which were all unique, compared to the control. Both of *Bbu I* and *BshT I* produced unique bands as well. All of the polymorphic and unique bands varied quantitatively and qualitatively in length, concentration, relative mobility, or fractionation on the gel, while the monomorphic bands resist the restriction activity of *Afa I* and *AsiA I* enzymes. Furthermore, the effect of the restriction enzymes on the fungal DNA treated with *Rumex* aqueous extract resulted in 16 fragments (38.1%), while eight (50%) of the fragments were produced by *Bbu I*. In the case of *Ziziphus* setting, 13 DNA fragments were produced and most of them were by *Bbu I* and *Cla I* (30.1%, 4 each).

Differences in nucleotide sequences, induced by variable treatments, at target sites will result in different-sized DNA fragments (restriction fragment length polymorphisms, or RFLPs) and reflect the alteration in the genetic sequence as a more sensitive factor than protein as it predicts the possible changes in the amino acids composition (Desikan and Narayanan, 2015). RFLP was commonly used to monitor the Fungicide Resistance of different species, in this respect, RFLP was used in a study on *Helminthosporium solani* that have been exhibited to thiophanate-methyl where the resistant mutations resulted in three sensitive DNA fragments at 62, 390, and 420 bp (Cunha and Rizzo, 2003). Another study reported the genetic resistance to *Quinone* outside inhibitor (QoI) and benzimidazole fungicides by *Cercospora beticola* where PCR-RFLP detected the two-point mutations in the fungal genes (Rosenzweig et al., 2015). So, RFLP method is suggested to be a useful screening tool for the genetic interaction between these plant extracts and the pathogenic fungi as it's less affected by time, space, and environmental conditions (Diba et al., 2014), besides, the variation of bands intensities might be due to the alterations of some DNA sequences and of the starting copy number of a particular DNA sequence within the genome (Forni et al., 2015).

In the current study, RAPD analysis was performed to evaluate the extent of the DNA alterations in the growth of *H. rostratum* treated with *Rumex* and *Ziziphus* aqueous extracts, separately. The usage of five different primer sets exhibited distinctive quantitative and qualitative alterations in the electrophoretic banding pattern of DNA yielded from the treated fungal growth compared with control (**Table 4** and **Figure 4**). Two primers (*P-10* and *P-12*) succeeded sensitively to produce clear reproducible DNA bands and gave satisfactory results with many alterations in the RAPD profiles. The total of seven polymorphic unique bands was obtained with *P-12* primer set with a total polymorphism of 87.5%. Furthermore, the obvious variation of fragments amplified by *P-12* primers indicated a strong genetic alteration or mutagenesis in the fungal DNA either between the untreated control and treated fungus or between the two different plants extracts.

RAPD markers is an easy technique that can test the genetic similarity and phylogenetic analysis (Irfan et al., 2017). Similar to RFLP, RAPD had been previously used to assess the mutational resistance of some fungi such as strains of *Fusarium graminearum* and *Fusarium poae* which are famous Wheat phytopathogens (Kuzdraliński et al., 2017). The current RAPD profile revealed that probable DNA damages induced by various plant extracts (*Rumex* and *Ziziphus*) as shown in the different amplified DNA band sizes, the intensity of each band, disappearance of normal band and appearance of new PCR products produced by the selected primer sets that resulted in higher polymorphism. Besides, based on the resulted data, it's clear that each treatment may lead to specific-level genotoxic effects on DNA of *H. rostratum* as shown with *P-12* primer. Also, the produced unique bands, in addition to the disappeared bands, suggest that the phytochemical composition of these plants, which is mostly phenolic, can induce an antimicrobial activity against specific pathogens by controlling their genetic material (Gatto et al., 2011; da Silva et al., 2017).

For more confirmation, we tested the DNA damage in the nuclei of the fungal cells by COMET assay. DNA damage was observed for the applied control and aqueous plant extracts (*Rumex* and *Ziziphus*) treatments, in fungal nuclei. The effects of treatments measured as tail DNA and tail moment are presented in Table 5 and Figure 5. The nuclear DNA of fungal nuclei acquires the appearance of a comet, with a head (undamaged DNA) and a tail (damaged DNA or percent-migrated DNA). The amount of DNA in the tail correlates with the number

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of DNA strand breaks and thus indicates the extent of DNA damage percent DNA in tail, as this gives a clear indication of the appearance of the comets. The results showed a remarkable variation in the extent of DNA damage in nuclei of fungal cells treated with plant extracts; these variations reflecting the stress induced by these plant extracts. The highest level of tailed DNA was observed in fungal nuclei treated with *Rumex* aqueous extract (13%) with a tail length of 4.33 μm and a tail moment unit of 17.54. However, for *Ziziphus* aqueous extract, the tailed DNA reached to 10 % with tail length 4.27 μm and a tail moment unit of 15.19. These results compared with tailed DNA in the untreated setting where the value reached 4 % with tail length 2.31 μm and tail moment unit 3.53. The obtained data demonstrated that *Rumex* extract caused more damage to fungal nuclear DNA which might result in the reduction of the fungal genome stability, growth, and productivity. In agreement with our results, a recent study reported that *Zizyphus jujube*, produced in Algeria, has a strong antifungal effect on seven different fungal species that induces a remarkable ROS production which caused damage of the fungal DNA and suggested that the presence of active compounds such as *flavonoids*, *alkaloids*, and *leucoanthocyanins* might contribute to the growth reduction (Belmokhtar et al., 2020). A similar study showed that *Ziziphus oxyphylla* Edgew had a strong anti-oxidant activity because of its phenolic composition, as well (Ahmad et al., 2014). Another previous study showed that *Rumex crispus* L. revealed a higher antifungal activity against Trichophyton tonsurans, *Trichosporon mucoides*, *Penicillium aurantiogriseum*, *Penicillium chrysogenum*, *Candida glabrata*, and *Candida albicans* as it induces higher genotoxicity because of its *flavonoid* composition (Idris et al., 2019).

CONCLUSION

In summary, the aqueous extracts of two wild plants, *Rumex vesicarius* L. and *Ziziphus spinachristi* had a strong antifungal activity against *H. rostratum*. Treatment with these extracts induced several changes in both of the amino acids and DNA of the fungal cells. The changes occurred in the RFLP and RAPD profiles, and the COMET Assay of the treated fungi system were successfully a sensitive tool for the detection of DNA damage induced by the treatment and were considered potential and reliable assays for genotoxicity investigations. In conclusion, the reported molecular changes might be response for the phytochemically characterizations of the crud aqueous extract of *Rumex* and *Ziziphus* which may result in the different DNA alteration scenarios, as an evidence of genotoxicity, besides, the changes in the amino acids sequences that led to variable protein expression of the fungus *H. rostratum*. More investigations are required to screen the mutational changes by DNA sequences and variants reporting.

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TABLES

Table 1. SDS-PAGE bands analysis of the *H. rostratum* proteins treated with aqueous plant extracts.

Lanes Rows	Mol. Weight (KDa)	Lane Marker		Lanes of treatments						Polymorphism
				Control		<i>R. vesicarius</i>		<i>Z. spina-christi</i>		
		KDa	%	KDa	%	KDa	%	KDa	%	
1	250	1	13.7	0		0		0		
2	246.06	0		0		1	0.55	1	7.16	p
3	236.48	0		0		1	2.14	0		u
4	216.69	0		1	3.50	0		0		u
5	193.89	0		0		1	3.67	0		u
6	189.32	0		1	3.45	0		0		u
7	180.51	0		0		1	4.32	1	4.70	p
8	172.11	0		1	1.88	0		0		u
9	162.80	0		0		0		1	7.65	u
10	155.22	0		0		1	7.31	0		u
11	151.57	0		1	5.38	0		1	3.60	p
12	148	1	11.7	0		0		0		
13	145.51	0		0		1	3.88	0		u
14	143.88	0		0		0		1	3.69	u
15	138.30	0		0		1	4.47	1	1.36	p
16	124.94	0		1	10.20	0		0		u
17	124.23	0		0		0		1	6.03	u
18	123.53	0		0		1	9.00	0		u
19	115.44	0		0		1	8.77			u
20	114.79	0		1	16.00	0		1	11.10	p
21	104.87	0		0		1	2.69	0		u
22	104.28	0		0		0		1	4.25	u
23	99.11	0		0		0		1	14.60	u
24	98	1	26.7	0		0		0		
25	97.47	0		0		1	19.80	0		u
26	95.36	0		1	16.10	0		0		u
27	81	1		0		0		0		
28	79.63	0		1	4.79	1	11.90	1	14.90	m
29	74.58	0		1	14.00	0		0		u
30	64	1	18.5	0		0		0		
31	63.06	0		1	2.62	0		0		u
32	61.37	0		0		1	21.50	0		u
33	61.07	0		0		0		1	6.61	u
34	59	1	12.6	0		0		1	14.40	u
35	56.10	0		1	22.00	0		0		u
36	50	0		0		1	0.55	1	0.5	p
37	40	0		0		1	0.3	1	0.33	p
38	36	0	16.8	0		0		0		
39	26	0		0		0		1	0.33	u
Total bands (42)				11		15		16		U = 25 P = 7 M = 1
% (of total bands)				26.2		35.7		38.1		
Unique bands (U) % = 25/33 = 75.76						Polymorphic bands (P) % = 7/33 = 21.2				
Monomorphic (M) % = 1/33 = 3.03						Polymorphism %= 96.69				

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Table 2. Effect of the aqueous plant extracts on the essential and non-essential amino acids content of *H. rostratum* biomass.

Amino acids ($\mu\text{mol}/100\text{mg DW}$)	Control	<i>Rumex vesecarius</i>		<i>Z.spina-christi</i>	
		Amount	% Alteration	Amount	% Alteration
Essential Amino Acids (EAAs)					
Arginine	7.321	6.278	14.2	7.136	2.5
Histidine	0.496	0.429	13.5	0.463	6.7
Isoleucine	0.145	0.076	47.6	0.096	33.8
Leucine	0.230	0.167	27.4	0.127	44.8
Lysine	0.617	0.522	15.4	0.480	22.2
Methionine	0.230	0.244	6.1	0.263	14.3
Phenylalanine	0.266	0.320	20.3	0.346	30.1
Threonine	1.549	1.339	13.6	1.445	6.7
Valine	0.532	0.384	27.8	0.475	10.7
Total	11.386	9.759	1.6	10.831	4.9
Non-essential amino Acids (NEAAs)					
Alanine	2.408	1.715	28.8	1.817	24.5
Asparagine	0.399	0.333	16.5	0.252	36.8
Aspartic acid	2.819	2.295	18.6	1.888	33
Cystein	0.980	0.612	37.6	0.656	33.1
Glutamic acid	4.029	2.896	28.1	2.199	45.4
Glutamine	2.481	2.449	1.3	2.645	6.6
Proline	1.016	1.272	25.2	1.302	28.1
Tyrosine	0.133	0.114	14.3	0.102	23.3
Total	14.265	11.686	18.1	10.861	23.9
Total of EAAs and non-EAAs	25.651	21.445	16.4	21.692	15.4

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Table 3. RFLP products of DNA extracted from fungal growth (*H. rostratum*) treated with aqueous plant extracts (using restriction enzymes *Afa I*, *AsiA I*, *Bbu I*, *BshT I* and *Cla I*).

DNA Restriction Enzyme	Recognition site sequence	Genomic source	Fragment lengths (bp)	Total DNA fragments generated by restriction enzymes						Polymorphic bands						% of Total Polymorphism	
				Control	<i>R. vesicarius</i>	<i>Z. spina-christi</i>	Total bands		Unique		Non-Unique		Polymorphic		Monomorphic bands		
							No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No		%
1. <i>Afa I</i>	5'-GT↓AC-3'	<i>Acidiphilium facilis</i>	346-171	2	2	2	6	14.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	33.3	0
2. <i>AsiA I</i>	5'- A↓CCGGT-3'	<i>Arthrobacter sp. A7359</i>	367-159	2	2	2	6	14.3	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	33.3	0
3. <i>Bbu I</i>	5'-GCATG↓C-3'	<i>Bacillus circulans</i>	400-157	5	8	4	17	40.5	3	17.6	1	5.9	4	23.5	4	23.5	50
4. <i>BshT I</i>	5'-A↓CCGGT-3'	<i>Bacillus sphaericus Jo22-024</i>	380-357	1	2	1	4	9.5	1	25.0	-	-	1	25.0	1	25.0	50
5. <i>Cla I</i>	5'-AT↓CGAT-3'	<i>Caryophanonlatum L</i>	468-89	3	2	4	9	21.4	9	100	-	-	9	100	-	-	100
Overall Total				13	16	13	42	100	13	30.9	1	2.4	14	33.3	9	21.4	60.88
Percent of total bands in each lane				30.9	38.1	30.9											

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Table 4. RAPD-PCR amplification products of DNA extracted from fungal growth (*H. rostratum*) treated with aqueous plant extract using five random primers.

Primers Code	Primers Sequences 5' → 3'	Amplicon lengths (bp)	Total number of scorable bands						Polymorphic bands						Monomorphic bands		% of Total Polymorphism
			Control	<i>R. vesicarius</i>	<i>Z. spina-christi</i>	Total bands		Unique bands		Non - Unique bands		Polymorphic bands					
						No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%	No	%		
P-01	5'-TGCCGAGCTG-3'	1110-353	2	2	2	6	20	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	33.3	0	
P-02	5'-GAAACGGGTG-3'	1210	1	1	1	3	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	33.3	0	
P-09	5'-GTGATCGCAG -3'	1110	1	1	1	3	10	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	33.3	0	
P-10	5'-TCTGTGCTGG-3'	1854-70	3	3	3	9	30	-	-	-	-	-	-	3	33.3	0	
P-12	5'-AGTCAGCCAC-3'	1778-34	3	3	3	9	30	7	77.8	-	-	7	77.8	1	11.1	87.5	
Overall total			10	10	10	30	100	7	23.3	-	-	7	23.3	8	26.7	46.67	
Percent of total bands in each lane			33.33	33.33	33.33												

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Table 5. The extent of nuclear DNA damage in untreated (control) and treated fungus (*H.*

Treatments	Tailed %	Un-tailed %	Tail length μm	Tail DNA %	Tail Moment Unit
Control	4	96	2.31	1.53	3.53
<i>R. vesicarius</i>	13	87	4.33	4.05	17.54
<i>Z. spina-christi</i>	10	90	4.27	3.56	15.19

rostratum) nuclei with aqueous plant extracts.

FIGURES

Figure 1. SDS_PAGE stained with Coomassie Brilliant Blue stain to show the results for the *H. rostratum* treated with aqueous plants extracts. M) standard protein marker, C) *H. rostratum* untreated control, R) *H. rostratum* treated with *Rumex* aqueous extract, and Z) *H. rostratum* treated with *Ziziphus* aqueous extract.

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A) Essential Amino acids

B) Non-Essential Amino acids

Figure 2. Effect of aqueous plant extract treatments on A) the essential and B) non-essential amino acids content of *H. rostratum* biomass.

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Figure 3. DNA fragments profile produced by RFLP fingerprinting of *H. rostratum* dried biomass using four restrictions endonucleases *Afa I*, *AsiA I*, *Bbu I*, *BshT I* and *Cla I*. The lanes C) for untreated sample (Control), R) for *Rumex* aqueous extract and Z) for *Ziziphus* aqueous extract treatment. Lane (leader): refers to the leader DNA marker.

Figure 4. DNA banding pattern of RAPD analysis of aqueous plant extracts treated fungus (*H. rostratum*) DNA generated by five primers. C. untreated sample (Control); R. *Rumex* and Z. *Ziziphus* extracts treatments. M. the standard DNA marker.

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Figure 5. Comets assay show varying extent of DNA damage of fungus nuclei induced by the aqueous plant extract treatments. 1. Control; 2. *Rumex*; 3. *Ziziphus* extracts treatments.